

Modelling energy losses arising from overridden backtracking in utility-scale photovoltaic plants on slightly undulating terrain: Implementation in the SISIFO tool for performance pre-assessment

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ABSTRACT

Underperformance of utility-scale photovoltaic plants continues to be systematically reported. Based on a detailed analysis over one year of 10–15-minute measurements from over seven thousand single-axis trackers across seven utility-scale photovoltaic plants, this study identifies a previously unaddressed source of such underperformance: tracking irradiation gain during backtracking is lower than expected. Slight terrain unevenness forces tracker controllers to override optimal backtracking angles to avoid inter-row shading, reducing tracker tilt and direct irradiance collection compared to flat-terrain simulations. This leads to a new loss category, here denominated suboptimal backtracking losses, which remain hidden within standard performance indicators and create an unquantified gap between simulated and actual energy yield. To address this, three overridden backtracking models are developed to reproduce real tracker behaviour through (1) direct overriding of the tracking angle, (2) analytical overriding of inter-row spacing, and (3) a virtual ground slope representing unevenness. Implemented in SISIFO, an open-source photovoltaic simulation tool, the models' estimates better match real performance, allowing estimation of suboptimal backtracking losses and explaining up to 2% of irradiance capture losses relative to conventional flat-terrain approaches. At utility scale, this difference is large enough to affect annual energy yield predictions and plant profitability, quantifying backtracking-related underperformance.

1. Introduction

Tracking irradiation gain, TIG, is a dimensionless variable which can be defined as

$$\text{TIG}_T(\omega) = \frac{G_T(\omega) - G_T(0)}{G_T(0)}, \quad (1)$$

where $G_T(\omega)$ and $G_T(0)$ are, respectively, the in-plane and horizontal global irradiances collected at a given site over a time period T , with the in-plane case referring to a surface tilted at a generic angle ω . TIG is an important Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for photovoltaic (PV) systems because it directly affects the energy yield. Many consultancies received at the Instituto de Energía Solar of the Universidad Politécnica de Madrid (IES-UPM) suggest that the observed TIG in actual utility-scale one-axis tracking PV plants is often lower than expected from the simulation of their energy yield performed at the project design phase for addressing bankability. In annual terms, the observed TIG values in these plants range between 10 and 20% below the expected ones, corresponding to approximately 1%–3% lower annual in-plane global irradiation collection with respect to the theoretical reference case.

Maybe, that can help explain why P50 energy yield estimates (median expected energy production) have historically been overly optimistic, as persistently reported by specialized studies [1]. It is worth noting that this issue does not affect either the Performance Ratio (PR) or the availability of the PV plant, which are usually the parameters used as the basis for contractual PV plant operation surveillance. Perhaps for this reason, despite its relevance in practice, this problem has gone unnoticed until now in the open literature.

This paper presents the case of seven different PV plants comprising trackers of five different manufactures and deployed on horizontal terrains. Our analysis revealed that the crux of the matter is that the simulation exercise assumed the terrain to be a perfectly horizontal surface, as incorporated in widely used software such as PVsyst[®] [2]. However, the real terrain presents some unevenness, resulting in slight differences in axis height between trackers, which therefore are no longer coplanar. Then, in case the tracking rotating angle takes the simulated value, it happens that during the backtracking period such height differences might lead to mutual shading between tracker rows.

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Nomenclature	
Abbreviation	Description
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
PV	Photovoltaic
IES-UPM	Instituto de Energía Solar, Universidad Politécnica de Madrid
PR	Performance Ratio
SCADA	Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition
TMY	Typical Meteorological Year
SISIFO	Photovoltaic Systems Simulator
BT	Backtracking
GCR	Ground Coverage Ratio
TST	True Solar Time
AC	Alternating Current
DC	Direct Current
MPPT	Maximum Power Point Tracking

Symbol	Description	Units
TIG	Tracking irradiation gain (subscript T indicates integration over period T)	[-]
G_T	Global irradiation collected over a time period T	[kWh m ⁻²]
ω	Tracker rotation angle	[deg]
α	Solar azimuth angle	[deg]
L_{C0}	Distance between adjacent PV rows relative to row width	[-]
γ'	Projected solar elevation angle on the working domain	[deg]
ω_{1DC}	Backtracking-corrected rotation angle	[deg]
Δh	Height difference between PV rows relative to row width	[-]
ω_C^U	Angular correction for terrain unevenness	[deg]
ω_{1D}	True tracking angle	[deg]
ω_C^{BT}	Angular correction for backtracking	[deg]
t	Time	[TST]
T_R	Sunrise time	[TST]
T_{BTR}	Morning backtracking termination time	[TST]
T_{BTS}	Afternoon backtracking initiation time	[TST]
T_S	Sunset time	[TST]
T_{V_R}	Visible sunrise time (sloping terrain)	[TST]
T_{V_S}	Visible sunset time (sloping terrain)	[TST]
ω_{TA}	Tracker target angular position	[deg]
ω_{TA}^ω	Tracker target angular position adjusted by ω	[deg]
L_{C0C}^U	L_{C0} corrected for terrain unevenness	[-]
L_{C0}^{BL}	Terrain-unevenness correction of L_{C0}	[-]
ω_{TA}^{BL}	Tracker target angular position adjusted by L_{C0}	[deg]
$\omega_C^{BT\&L}$	Angular correction for backtracking considering a terrain unevenness-aware L_{C0}	[deg]
β_{CS}	Cross-axis slope angle	[deg]
$L_{C\beta}$	PV row horizontal spacing considering cross-axis slope β_{CS} relative to row width	[-]
ω_{TA}^β	Tracker target angular position adjusted by β_{CS}	[deg]
$\omega_C^{BT\&\beta}$	Angular correction for backtracking considering a cross-axis slope β_{CS}	[deg]
ΔT_{BTR}	Morning backtracking time interval	[TST]
ΔT_{BTS}	Afternoon backtracking time interval	[TST]
a_0	Method 1 correction at outer BT boundaries	[-]
a_{BT}	Method 1 correction at inner BT transition boundaries	[-]
b_0	Method 2 correction at outer BT boundaries	[-]
b_{BT}	Method 2 correction at inner BT transition boundaries	[-]
c_0	Method 3 correction at outer BT boundaries	[-]
c_{BT}	Method 3 correction at inner BT transition boundaries	[-]
ΔTIG_A	Relative annual deviation of tracking irradiation gain	[-]
ΔG_A	Relative annual deviation of in-plane irradiation	[-]
G_A	Global irradiation collected over an annual period	[kWh m ⁻²]
ω_E	Experimental SCADA-recorded tracker rotation angle	[deg]
$\Delta\omega$	Angular deviation between target and measured tracker position	[deg]
$\omega_{E,i}$	Experimental SCADA-recorded rotation angle of tracker i	[deg]
$\Delta\omega_i$	Target-to-measured angular deviation of tracker i	[deg]

To avoid this shading, which would otherwise be shocking to the eye and detrimental in terms of power output and formation of hot spots, the rotation angle is overridden by decreasing its tilt, at the price of reducing the irradiance collection. Because all real PV plant terrains have unevenness to a greater or lesser extent, we believe that this issue is general and not limited to the cases analysed here, identifying a new source of deviation between simulated and actual irradiance collection, which leads to a new loss category denominated in this study as suboptimal backtracking losses. This justifies its consideration in the open literature, in which, as far as we know, it has never been previously referenced.

The open treatment of this problem among the PV plant market actors is made difficult by the fact that its formal recognition translates into a reduction in the energy expected for the base case and, consequently, in the amount of bank financing. Hence, to understand how tracking angles are overridden to implement corrections for slight terrain unevenness and the consequent impact on TIG, we first proceeded as a case of reverse-engineering, observing the difference between the ideal (as calculated to avoid shading in a perfectly horizontal terrain) and the actual (as recorded in the SCADA of the PV plant) rotation angles to disclose the applied correction algorithm. To this end, we first postulated several possible algorithms to consider the slight terrain unevenness when calculating the tracker rotation angle, and then we analysed which one best fits the in-field observed angles in each case. Therefore, the aim of these backtracking algorithms is to account for slight terrain unevenness, so that the estimated energy production better reflects the real one by considering the overridden actions in tracker positioning performed in-field. They are based on different analytical modifications of the variables involved in the backtracking computation, which will be described later in this work. These algorithms can improve the backtracking approaches proposed in Fernández-Ahumada et al. [3], support design adaptations for specialized PV configurations [4], and enhance economic and performance assessments of single-axis tracking PV plants [5]. Finally, we simulated the corresponding TIG based on the Typical Meteorological Year (TMY) of the location. For that, we have implemented the ability to model such correction algorithms in SISIFO, an open software developed by the IES-UPM (freely accessible at <https://sisifo.info>).

The manuscript is structured into five sections. Following the Introduction, the second section identifies the effects of implementing backtracking in real PV plants installed on slightly uneven terrain, based on observations from actual operating PV plants. The third section proposes models for backtracking algorithms that account for slight terrain unevenness by overriding the parameters on which the tracking angles depend during computation. This section also analyzes the impact of these models on solar irradiation and provides details on the implementation of the proposed models in SISIFO, making them accessible to any user. Section 4 presents a comparison between the models proposed in Section 3 and the experimental data collected from the SCADA systems of the analysed PV plants, evaluating both the differences in the angular behaviour of the trackers and in the resulting TIG values. The last section summarizes the main conclusions derived from this work.

2. Backtracking on slightly uneven terrain

The principles of tracking and backtracking for PV arrays are well known from many years ago on a horizontal surface [6], extended recently for sloping terrain [7]. Here, we will limit ourselves to pointing out the impact of slight unevenness during the backtracking period. Fig. 1 shows the 2D geometry of backtracking for multi-row PV arrays on horizontal terrain; further geometric details can be found in Marion et al. [8]. The drawing plane is orthogonal to the tracker rows, which point to a certain azimuth α . In the normal case of North–South oriented axes ($\alpha = 0$), the drawing plane is perpendicular to the meridian plane. The cross-section of the generator rows in this plane is shown

Fig. 1. 2D geometry of backtracking for multi-row PV arrays on horizontal terrain. The drawing plane is orthogonal to the tracker rows. The cross-section of the PV modules is shown in blue, the projection of the Sun rays in dashed yellow, the shaded ground areas in red, and the unshaded ones in dark yellow. (a) Standard backtracking situation. (b) Shading effects caused by terrain unevenness. (c) Angular overcorrection applied to avoid shading due to unevenness. (d) Light bands appearing on the ground when the overcorrection is applied on flat terrain.

in blue, while the yellow dashed lines represent the projection of the Sun rays on the drawing plane. Hereafter, all distances in the working domain are normalized by the row width and are therefore dimensionless. For simplicity, the trackers are depicted without elevation above the ground, which is coloured red when shaded and dark yellow when unshaded. The distance between two adjacent rows and relative to the row width is L_{C0} , where the subscript C means *Crosswise*, consistent with the drawing plane being orthogonal to the tracker rows, and the subscript 0 indicates that the distance is measured on the horizontal. Notice that, due to the distance normalization, the inverse of L_{C0} corresponds to the ground coverage ratio (GCR), allowing simulation results to be compared across PV plants independently of the generator cross-section. Additionally, γ' is the elevation angle of the Sun projection onto the drawing plane. The rotation angle of the tracker, generally denoted as ω , is measured around the tracker axis from the horizontal along the shortest path, being positive in the clockwise direction and negative in the counterclockwise direction. This sign and path convention will be followed for all angle measurements hereafter. Fig. 1(a) shows the position of the tracker rows during backtracking in case of perfectly flat ground. The rotation angle is denoted ω_{IDC} , where ID and C , in the subindex, respectively, means *Ideal* and *Corrected for backtracking*. The reason for this nomenclature is the consistency with previous published works [9]. This angle ω_{IDC} is calculated just to avoid mutual shading between the tracker rows, as explained in Schneider et al. [10]. Note that the shade of the upper edge of the front row impinges just in the bottom edge of the rear row, which results in the ground being totally shaded. Fig. 1(b) shows that when the ground is not perfectly flat but rather presents some slight unevenness, this translates to differences in height between rows, Δh , which, if ω_{IDC} is maintained, causes the formation of shading in some rows. The dashed blue segments in this figure indicate the position that the rows would occupy if the terrain were perfectly flat. Fig. 1(c) describes how an overcorrection for slight unevenness ω_C^U , where the superscript U means *Unevenness*, in addition to the correction for backtracking,

prevents such undesirable shading. The dashed blue segments here represent the configuration that would result if ω_{IDC} were maintained (and the same applies to Fig. 1(d)). However, the situation in Fig. 1(c) only occurs in rows with a higher row in front of them. In other cases, with the front row at lower height, keeping ω_{IDC} causes strips of light to appear on the ground (Fig. 1(d)). In fact, these strips, whose irradiance is lost for the PV modules, are the clearest symptom that the tracker controller is applying some overcorrection. Consequently, the irradiation gain under clear sky conditions is lower than the calculated assuming a perfectly flat ground, as the 2D view-factor model of the commonly used PV simulation softwares, such as PVSyst® or SISIFO, consider.

Fig. 2 shows some photographs taken in a representative commercial utility-scale PV plant. Pictures shown in Figs. 2(a) and 2(b) clearly indicate misalignment, i.e., height differences of the row axes in the East–West and North–South directions, which are no longer coplanar as in the simulated scenario due to slight terrain unevenness. These two pictures were taken during the central hours of the day, when all the rows are kept perpendicular to the Sun and, therefore, there are no irradiance losses with respect to the simulation performed at the design. However, the pictures shown in Figs. 2(c) and 2(d) were taken during the backtracking period, and the strips of light appearing in the ground mean that a backtracking overcorrection is being applied and, consequently, there is a loss of irradiance compared to the simulated case. It must be highlighted that this loss is not captured by the PR, because the in-plane irradiation used to compute the theoretical energy production, and thus to calculate the PR, is typically measured with pyranometers in the inclined plane or, more accurately, with reference modules. Thus, since the PR is computed as the ratio between the theoretical and the actual measured energy, and both are affected by the in-plane irradiance losses due to unevenness, the PR does not detect the effect of tracker angular misalignments. Consequently, this loss remains hidden from SCADA systems, which do not display the ω_{IDC} value but instead show the so-called target position of the trackers, which

Fig. 2. Misalignments of the row axes due to ground unevenness in the (a) East–West and (b) North–South directions. These images were taken during the central hours of the day, when the trackers keep the PV modules perpendicular to the Sun, avoiding irradiance losses. Images (c) and (d) show light bands appearing on the ground during backtracking, which represent irradiance losses.

already includes the overcorrection for unevenness. Thus, the effect only becomes evident when comparing the energy actually measured in a real PV plant, such as those under study, with the energy expected from the simulation, which is consistently higher.

3. Unevenness correction of the rotation angle and irradiation impact

If there were no corrections for unevenness, Lorenzo et al. [11] shows that the following equations apply

$$\omega_{ID} = \frac{\pi}{2} - \gamma', \tag{2}$$

$$\cos \omega_C^{BT} = \min [L_{C0} \cdot \cos \omega_{ID}, 1], \tag{3}$$

$$\omega_{DC} = \omega_{ID} - \omega_C^{BT}, \tag{4}$$

where ω_{ID} is the value of ω when the PV array is kept perpendicular to the Sun, sometimes referred to as the “true” angle [12], and ω_C^{BT} is the correction for backtracking, where the subscript *C* denotes *Correction* and the superscript *BT* denotes *Backtracking*. The convention used for computing this angle is that it is measured around the rotation axis from the corrected module position to the true angle along the shortest path, with positive values for clockwise rotation and negative values otherwise, as is customary. It should also be noted that all angular quantities in this work are expressed in degrees.

Obviously, the computation of any of the tracker angles depends on the time variable *t*, which has not been explicitly indicated to simplify the notation. It is also worth noting that the length of the shadow cast

by a tracker row on the ground is equal to the inverse of $\cos \omega_{ID}$ [13], and that the backtracking correction applies only when this length is greater than L_{C0} . Hence, in the morning, the backtracking (BT) period extends from sunrise to the moment when the shadow length is equal to L_{C0} . We denote these moments by T_R and T_{BTR} , respectively. Similarly, in the afternoon the BT period begins when the shadow length is again equal to L_{C0} and ends at sunset, moments that we denote T_{BTS} and T_S , respectively. These values are standard calculations in any PV simulation software, as functions of latitude, time, and ground coverage ratio. In fact, for greater clarity, these instants are highlighted along the abscissa in Fig. 3(a), which shows the time evolution of the angles ω_{ID} , ω_{DC} and ω_C^{BT} during the spring equinox for a simulated PV plant in Mexico installed on horizontal terrain. The time axis is expressed in units of True Solar Time (TST), with 0 corresponding to midday. In the following, all time-dependent plots in this work will use TST on the time axis. Notice that when the terrain is completely horizontal, the two daily backtracking periods are perfectly symmetrical. However, when the terrain presents a cross-axis slope, this symmetry no longer holds. This can be seen in Fig. 3(b), which is analogous to Fig. 3(a) but considers a 10° East–West slope measured from the horizontal. In such cases, it becomes evident that the backtracking periods are no longer symmetrical, and two new important time reference points arise, denoted as T_{VR} and T_{VS} , which indicate the moments when sunrise and sunset become visible for the sloping terrain, respectively. This justifies the addition of the letter *V* in the subscript. Finally, note that in Fig. 3, the corrected angle ω_{DC} is also subject to the physical limit of the tracker, which in the present example is set to 55°. This constitutes a slight abuse of notation, adopted for the sake of simplicity, and the same criterion will be followed in the subsequent figures, even

Fig. 3. Tracker angular behaviour throughout the day for a simulated PV plant in Mexico on the spring equinox, with the abscissa expressed in True Solar Time (TST). (a) Case with perfectly horizontal terrain. (b) Case with a 10° East-West cross-axis slope. The figures highlight the main characteristic instants of tracker operation: sunrise (T_R), end of the morning backtracking period (T_{BTR}), beginning of the afternoon backtracking period (T_{BTS}), and sunset (T_S). The additional instant T_{VR} indicates the moment when sunrise becomes visible on sloping terrain.

though this limit is not considered in the definition given in Eq. (4). Consequently, backtracking periods may extend beyond this physical limit.

In practice, real tracker controllers calculate the so-called target position, denoted as ω_{TA} , which slightly differs from ω_{IDC} . In particular, ω_{TA} is likely overridden to incorporate the correction for slight terrain unevenness, which can be achieved by directly altering the value of ω_{IDC} . In that case, the target angle is denoted as ω_{TA}^ω , where the superscript ω indicates that the correction is obtained by directly modifying the angular value. That is, ω_{TA}^ω can be expressed as

$$\omega_{TA}^\omega = \omega_{IDC} - \omega_C^U, \quad (5)$$

where ω_C^U denotes the angular unevenness correction (see Fig. 1(c)). Note also that the target position of the modules is measured from the horizontal around the tracker axis, as is the case for the ω_{IDC} angle.

However, in principle, computing corrections for unevenness could be achieved in alternative ways, for example, by analytically overriding any of the variables from which ω_{IDC} is derived, such as L_{C0} . For that, analogously to Eq. (5) a distance corrected for unevenness L_{C0C}^U can be defined as

$$L_{C0C}^U = L_{C0} - L_{BL}^U, \quad (6)$$

where L_{BL}^U is equal to the width of the band of light appearing on the ground in the model with ideally flat terrain when the unevenness correction is applied. This justifies the subscript *BL* (*Band Light*) and the superscript *U* (*Unevenness*), as illustrated in Fig. 4(a), where the drawing plane and colour coding follow the same convention as in Fig. 1. It should be noted that this inter-row spacing override only affects simulation input parameters and does not require any physical modification of the PV plant layout.

The target position is then calculated as

$$\omega_{TA}^L = \omega_{ID} - \omega_C^{BT\&L}, \quad (7)$$

with

$$\cos \omega_C^{BT\&L} = \min [L_{C0C}^U \cos \omega_{ID}, 1], \quad (8)$$

where, the target angle notation ω_{TA}^L has been modified to introduce the superscript *L*, which indicates that the new correction is achieved by overriding the distance L_{C0} . Likewise, the superscript *BT&L* in the correction for backtracking has been modified from the standard notation ω_C^{BT} to emphasize that, in this method, the correction is applied by overriding the inter-row distance L_{C0} to account for unevenness. These equations are analogous to Eqs. (3) and (4) and provide an alternative method for calculating the target angle of the trackers.

For the sake of clarity, in this paper we restricted ourselves to presenting the equations corresponding to the case of horizontal ground, although the same ideas apply to the general case of trackers on

sloping ground. In fact, Ramírez-Ledesma et al. [14] shows that, when considering a cross-axis slope angle β_{CS} , the backtracking correction $\omega_C^{BT\&\beta}$ is defined as

$$\cos \omega_C^{BT\&\beta} = \min \left[L_{C\beta} \cdot \frac{\cos(\omega_{ID} - \beta_{CS})}{\cos \beta_{CS}}, 1 \right], \quad (9)$$

with

$$L_{C\beta} = L_{C0} (1 + \tan \omega_{ID} \tan \beta_{CS})^{-1}, \quad (10)$$

where $L_{C\beta}$ is the horizontal distance between the rows. Note that the superscript notation for the applied backtracking correction has been modified by introducing an additional β , explicitly indicating that a cross-axis slope β_{CS} is considered in this case. Also, note that β_{CS} is measured from the horizontal, and that when $\beta_{CS} = 0$, Eq. (9) reverts to Eq. (3). The point here is that accounting for the correction for unevenness can also be achieved by overriding the value of β_{CS} . Fig. 4(b) shows, again for a horizontal terrain, the equivalence between modifying the rotation angle and assuming a certain slope of the ground. Now, the target position becomes

$$\omega_{TA}^\beta = \omega_{ID} - \omega_C^{BT\&\beta}, \quad (11)$$

where the superscript β in ω_{TA}^β indicates that the target angle is obtained considering a cross-axis slope β_{CS} .

Thus, from Eqs. (5), (7) and (11), it is clear that the target angle computed in this work is overridden to include a correction for unevenness, which can be achieved through at least three different approaches: (1) by overriding the tracker angle, (2) the distance L_{C0} , or (3) the cross-axis slope β_{CS} . These three approaches correspond to the three models considered in this work for anticipating suboptimal backtracking losses during the simulation phase and also quantifying backtracking-related underperformance on current PV plants. Figs. 5–7 show the flowcharts summarizing these three proposed models for incorporating slight terrain unevenness effects into backtracking algorithms. Therefore, to continue the computation of the target angle, it only remains to define the variables on which its calculation depends. To this end, we postulated linear equations for these three ways of implementing a correction for unevenness, each of which defines the corresponding variables at every instant t of the day. Thus, when directly overriding the value of ω_{IDC} , the following equations are considered,

$$\omega_C^U(t) = \begin{cases} a_0 + \frac{a_{BT} - a_0}{\Delta T_{BTR}} (t - T_R), & T_R \leq t \leq T_{BTR}, \\ a_0 + \frac{a_{BT} - a_0}{\Delta T_{BTS}} (T_S - t), & T_{BTS} \leq t \leq T_S, \\ 0, & T_{BTR} \leq t \leq T_{BTS}, \end{cases} \quad (12)$$

Fig. 4. Illustration of the equivalence between modifying the rotation angle and (a) changing the distance between tracker axes, represented by the width of the light band appearing on the ground when the unevenness correction is applied, and (b) varying the ground slope. The drawing plane and colour coding follow the same convention as in Fig. 1.

Fig. 5. Flowchart of Model 1, based on direct modification of the tracker rotation angle.

where the coefficients a_0 and a_{BT} are, respectively, the corrections at the extremes of the daily BT periods (a_0 at the start of the first backtracking period and at the end of the last, a_{BT} at the end of the morning BT period and at the beginning of the afternoon one, and are therefore angular magnitudes measured in degrees), and

$$\Delta T_{BTR} = T_{BTR} - T_{VR}, \quad \Delta T_{BTS} = T_{VS} - T_{BTS}. \quad (13)$$

Note that when the terrain is assumed to be horizontal, $\Delta T_{BTR} = \Delta T_{BTS}$ and $T_{VR} = T_R$, $T_{VS} = T_S$. Also, notice that, in this case for computing the target angle, T_{BTR} and T_{BTS} are not altered by the unevenness correction.

On the other hand, if consideration of slight terrain unevenness in the target angle calculation is performed by analytically overriding the row spacing L_{C0} , the following linear equations are proposed for the calculation of L_{BL}^U ,

$$L_{BL}^U(t) = \begin{cases} b_0 + \frac{b_{BT} - b_0}{\Delta T_{BTR}}(t - T_R), & T_R \leq t \leq T_{BTR}, \\ b_0 + \frac{b_{BT} - b_0}{\Delta T_{BTS}}(T_S - t), & T_{BTS} \leq t \leq T_S, \\ 0, & T_{BTR} \leq t \leq T_{BTS}. \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

Here, the coefficients b_0 and b_{BT} are the corrections at the extremes of the BT periods which correspond to a normalized distance and are therefore dimensionless. This time, T_{BTR} and T_{BTS} are altered by the unevenness correction because the corresponding shadow length cast by the tracker row at the end of the morning backtracking period and at the beginning of the afternoon backtracking period is no longer L_{C0} , but rather $L_{C0} - b_{BT}$.

Finally, a set of linear equations is provided to calculate the daily cross-axis slope β_{CS} to be used if the unevenness correction is applied by assuming sloping terrain, as expressed in Eq. (11),

$$\beta_{CS}(t) = \begin{cases} c_0 + \frac{c_{BT} - c_0}{\Delta T_{BTR}}(t - T_{VR}), & T_{VR} \leq t \leq T_{BTR} \\ c_0 + \frac{c_{BT} - c_0}{\Delta T_{BTS}}(T_S - t), & T_{BTS} \leq t \leq T_{VS} \\ 0, & T_{BTR} \leq t \leq T_{BTS} \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

The coefficients c_0 and c_{BT} represent the corrections at the extremes of the BT periods and are therefore angular magnitudes expressed in degrees. Again, T_{BTR} and T_{BTS} are computed taking into account the corresponding cross-axis slope angle, as well as T_{VR} and T_{VS} . As in the inter-row spacing approach (Model 2), this formulation overrides only the simulation input variables from which ω_{IDC} is derived and does not require any field-level intervention. Therefore, the method can be readily implemented using the software framework provided in this work.

It should be noted that we tested functions other than linear, but no improvements were observed that would justify the increased complexity. Also, to conclude this section, it should be emphasized that replacing ω_{IDC} with ω_{TA} implies deliberately abandoning the optimal backtracking strategy to follow an overridden backtracking aimed at minimizing shading effects caused by slight terrain unevenness.

3.1. Irradiation impact

Whichever the case, the unevenness correction decreases the tilt of the tracker plane during the BT periods, which in turn implies direct

Fig. 6. Flowchart of Model 2, considering analytical override of the inter-row spacing under terrain unevenness conditions.

Fig. 7. Flowchart of Model 3, accounting for slight unevenness effects through a hypothetical terrain slope.

irradiation losses. This is quantified in annual terms for TIG and G_A using the relative annual gain differences ΔTIG_A and ΔG_A , which are dimensionless quantities that have been defined as

$$\Delta TIG_A = \frac{TIG_A(\omega_{IDC}) - TIG_A(\omega_{TA})}{TIG_A(\omega_{IDC})}, \quad (16)$$

and

$$\Delta G_A = \frac{G_A(\omega_{IDC}) - G_A(\omega_{TA})}{G_A(\omega_{IDC})}, \quad (17)$$

where, to reflect the annual nature of the analysis, the previous used temporal subscript T has now been replaced by A .

It should be noted that unevenness corrections to avoid shading also affect the diffuse and reflected irradiance components, in addition to the direct component, especially in bifacial systems. However, this effect is usually not large enough to fully compensate for the loss of direct irradiance.

Furthermore, notice that this study is limited to assessing the impact on irradiation gain, which makes the results general and independent of the module characteristics. However, the effect under analysis on the energy yield occurs during the BT periods, that is, during intervals free from clipping and curtailment. Consequently, the impact of the studied tracking behaviour on the energy yield is not mitigated by the presence of such phenomena and, therefore, tends to increase its relevance in explaining the final differences between simulated and actual performance.

3.2. Implementation in SISIFO

SISIFO is a PV simulation software (freely accessible at <https://sisifo.info>) developed by the IES-UPM under the umbrella of the European projects *PVCROPS* [15], *MASLOWATEN* [16], and currently *PVOP* [17]. Main models used in SISIFO for irradiance distribution [18], decomposition and transposition [19], and spectral correction [20] were presented in 2013 in Muñoz et al. [21], and can also be found in Lorenzo et al. [22]. SISIFO allows dealing with mutual shading [23], different tracking types [24], and both grid-connected and pumping PV systems [25]. SISIFO is also capable of simulating bifacial PV arrays on sloping terrains [14].

Now, we have implemented in SISIFO the capability to account for suboptimal backtracking losses due to slight terrain unevenness by incorporating the three target angle models described above (Model 1, where the target angle is obtained through Eq. (5) by overriding the tracker rotation angle; Model 2, where the target angle is obtained through Eq. (7) by analytically overriding the inter-row distance; and Model 3, where the target angle is overridden through Eq. (11) by considering a cross-axis slope of the terrain). It is worth mentioning that the particular case of the second model (case ω_{TA}^L) with $b_0 = b_{BT}$, that is, with a distance between rows which is constant, although different from the geometric one, can be treated with any standard PV software. The same applies to the third target correction analysed (case ω_{TA}^β) with $c_0 = c_{BT}$, provided the software is able of dealing with sloping terrains.

Table 1
Technical features of the PV plants under study.

PV plant	Country	Tracker manufacturer/type	Number of analysed trackers	$L_{c0}/[]$	Rotation limit/[°]
1	Egypt	Multi-row	5	2.26	55
2.1	Brazil	Multi-row	60	2.55	55
2.2	Brazil	Multi-row	52	2.55	55
3	Chile	Multi-row	2493	2.26	60
4.1	Mexico	Multi-row	533	3.20	55
4.2	Mexico	Multi-row	78	3.20	55
5	Spain	Multi-row	2017	2.56	55
6.1	Spain	Multi-row	814	2.71	55
6.2	Spain	Multi-row	1059	2.71	55
7	Chile	Single-row	105	2.74	55

For example, SISIFO allows PV simulations on sloping terrain, including bifacial systems. Therefore, it can be used to adjust the rotation angle of each individual tracker in order to mitigate energy losses caused by terrain unevenness.

4. In field observations

Looking to disclose the slight unevenness correction algorithms implemented in real PV plants, we contrasted the experimentally observed tracking rotation angle values, ω_E (where the subindex E denotes *Experimental*), recorded by the SCADA of several large utility-scale PV plants, with the corresponding calculated values for perfectly flat terrain, i.e., with ω_{TA} and ω_{IDC} . All the plants are one-axis tracked and deployed on horizontal terrain. Table 1 shows the relevant data of the PV plants. Notice that PV plants 2, 4, and 6 each consist of two distinct parcels, denoted by a numerical extension appended to the plant name. The names of the plants and the tracker manufacturers are kept confidential.

It must be understood that, even in the absence of mechanical errors or failures, due to the stepper motion of the trackers and the fact that they are not necessarily synchronized but some move successively, there is a difference between ω_E and the target angle provided by the real tracker controllers. Thus, before proceeding, it is important to note that ω_E exhibits two distinct sources of misalignment with respect to ω_{IDC} . The first, which is the focus of this study, arises from overriding the target angle to compensate for slightly uneven terrain and is included in the models presented for computing ω_{TA} . The second source of misalignment is inherent to any PV plant: trackers require a certain amount of time to reach their target angle because not all rows rotate simultaneously, as this would generate peaks in power consumption when powered by AC. Even in single-row DC-fed systems, the wireless transmission of the target angle command from the central controller to each of the thousands of trackers introduces communication delays, and the movement sequence typically starts from the rows farthest from the sun and progresses toward those closest to it, meaning that rotation is not instantaneous.

In real operating data, both components appear combined, although they can be analysed separately. Thus, the experimental tracker angle can be expressed as

$$\omega_E = \omega_{TA} + \Delta\omega, \quad (18)$$

where $\Delta\omega$ represents the difference between target and actual positions resulting from the second source of misalignment. $\Delta\omega$ can adopt positive or negative values and, although its variation is not truly random since it follows specific control algorithms and operational causes, it can be regarded as random noise when analysed over the entire PV plant. Typical thresholds for triggering movement range from 1° to 3°.

What we analysed for the i th-tracker is the time series of values of

$$\omega_{E,i} - \omega_{TA} = \Delta\omega_i, \quad (19)$$

where i ranges from 1 to the total number of trackers available for a given PV plant. The angle ω_{TA} is calculated for each plant and for the

different possibilities described in previous section. Then, we selected the one that best fits $\omega_{E,i}$, i.e., the one leading to the minimum $\Delta\omega_i$ values.

Furthermore, SISIFO can also simulate using the measured values $\omega_{E,i}$ to assess the production that a PV plant would achieve under these empirical angles, and to compare it with the expected performance obtained from the design phase. The results from this comparison are generally higher than those obtained when comparing the performance calculated using ω_{IDC} and ω_{TA} , since some measured angles may significantly deviate from their target positions due to operational anomalies often observed in real operating conditions. These anomalies may arise from factors such as the activation of wind stow positions, fire alarms, or control and communication failures that immobilize one or more trackers. The resulting angular positions not only reduce the energy yield of the affected trackers but also cause mutual shading on adjacent trackers and additional Maximum Power Point Tracking (MPPT) mismatch losses when multiple trackers share the same inverter without individual MPPT channels.

As an illustration of such behaviour, Figs. 8(a) and 8(b) show the angular trajectories of two different trackers from the same PV plant during the spring equinox, compared with ω_{IDC} . In fact, in some of the analysed PV plants, these anomalies in the tracker operation led to additional production losses exceeding 3% when compared with the results obtained using ω_{IDC} during the design phase. Consequently, total annual energy losses exceeding 5% due to tracking effects, relative to the idealized simulation of a PV plant with all trackers in their optimal and shade-free positions, are not uncommon and represent a significant operational impact.

It is also worth noting that even when trackers follow the target positions as expected, there is an associated measurement uncertainty in $\omega_{E,i}$, which can be typically obtained from the trackers' inclinometers. Empirical observations across multiple trackers and positions indicate that this uncertainty is around 0.5° and rarely exceeds 1.5°.

To streamline the subsequent analysis, we focused on a single representative tracker per PV plant. Nevertheless, due to the temporal and tracker dependence of $\Delta\omega_i$, it is necessary to assess whether angular deviations across trackers within the same PV plant are statistically significant. To this end, a pre-selection of trackers was performed based on data availability and quality, ensuring that only those with valid and consistent measurements were included in the analysis, discarding, for example, those shown in Fig. 8. Although the full methodological details are beyond the scope of this paper, the application of the Scheirer-Ray-Hare test [26] indicates no evidence of statistically significant differences among trackers of the same PV plant. This result supports the assumption that the behaviour of a single tracker can reliably represent the overall tracking performance of each PV plant. Thus, henceforward, indexed references to individual trackers can be omitted when considering angular positions or corrections. While this finding is consistent with expectations, it is particularly relevant in two scenarios: in single-row trackers, where individual tracker adjustments are technically feasible, and in multirotor systems with sequential movement, where temporal effects might introduce more pronounced angular differences between interconnected rows.

Fig. 8. Real angular behaviour (ω_E) of two different trackers, shown in (a) and (b), from PV plant 4.1 during the spring equinox, compared with the analytical backtracking-corrected rotation angle ω_{IDC} . Anomalies in the tracker behaviour can be observed not only during the backtracking periods but also outside of them.

Fig. 9. Evolution through the spring equinox of tracker rotation angles and angular deviations in PV plant 4.1. The figure shows the experimental tracker angle ω_E , the backtracking-corrected angle ω_{IDC} and the target angle ω_{TA}^L , as well as the deviations between measured and modelled angles. Note that the phenomenon is practically symmetrical in the morning and in the afternoon.

As a representative example, Fig. 9 describes the evolution throughout an equinox day of ω_E , ω_{IDC} , ω_{TA}^L , $\omega_E - \omega_{IDC}$, and $\omega_E - \omega_{TA}^L$ for a representative tracker of PV plant 4.1. The time is given in hours of True Solar Time (TST), with 0 corresponding to midday, as previously explained. The left axis displays the evolution of the rotation angles ω_E , ω_{IDC} , and ω_{TA}^L , while the right axis shows the absolute differences $\omega_E - \omega_{IDC}$ and $\omega_E - \omega_{TA}^L$. The morning behaviour is practically symmetrical to that of the afternoon, and Fig. 10 shows a zoom of the morning period. Fig. 11 displays the corresponding histograms of $\omega_E - \omega_{IDC}$ and $\omega_E - \omega_{TA}^L$, considering data registered in four representative days, the two equinoxes and the two solstices, restricted to the BT periods.

The depicted case corresponds to ω_{TA}^L with $b_0 = b_{BT} = 0.55$, which, after testing multiple unevenness correction configurations, is the one that leads to the minimum $\Delta\omega$ values. A simulation exercise for the TMY of the site shows that the associated irradiation losses are $\Delta TIG_A = 8.2\%$ and $\Delta G_A = 2.0\%$ (Table 2).

Fig. 12 shows the same type of analysis as Fig. 10 for all the other plants considered in this paper. The corresponding numerical results are summarized in Table 2. Care must be taken to note that all PV plants analysed here are located on horizontal terrain and have equally spaced trackers, which makes it easier to identify the applied corrections. Nevertheless, SISIFO also allows simulations on sloping terrains.

After the previous study, the following comments apply:

- In all the PV systems, some type of slight unevenness correction affects the tracker rotation angle when BT is applied. This is true even for the case of single-row trackers. This behaviour

Fig. 10. Expanded view of the morning BT period of Fig. 9 for better visualization.

has been revealed through the analysis of operational data from real PV plants, which, despite knowing the optimal backtracking algorithms, override the parameters on which the analytical calculation of backtracking angles depends to avoid shading effects associated with slightly uneven terrain.

- ΔTIG_A and ΔG_A range from 4%–10% and 0.8%–2%, respectively. Large enough to significantly affect the profitability of PV plants.
- The most frequent correction consists of assuming a distance between tracker rows smaller than the real one. That is, computing ω_{TA}^L with $b_0 = b_{BT}$. This is likely to happen because it is particularly easy to implement in standard tracker controllers, because it does not require any software modification but only a change in input data. Interestingly, an equivalent approach to reduce shading effects on sloping terrain was previously proposed in Anderson et al. [27], based on manually adjusting the GCR input in the backtracking algorithm until shading losses are minimized.

4.1. Horizontal vs sloping terrain

We would like to emphasize that this study was conducted using real operating data from PV plants installed on horizontal terrain. As mentioned previously, this terrain is not completely horizontal, but slightly undulating. This results in the actual angles differing from those for which the plant was designed, and is the reason for this study: to

Fig. 11. Histograms of the differences between the empirical and simulated tracker angles for PV plant 4.1, (a) $\omega_E - \omega_{IDC}$ and (b) $\omega_E - \omega_{TA}^L$. In addition to the empirical histogram, a normal distribution is plotted in red using the mean and standard deviation of each dataset, showing a noticeably sharper distribution around the mean for (b).

Table 2

Summary of simulation results and best-fit parameters for each PV plant. The *Best fit* column specifies the target angle used and the coefficients applied in the corresponding Eqs. (12), (14) and (15).

PV plant	L_{C0} [-]	$G_A(0)$ [kWh/m ²]	$G_A(\omega_{IDC})$ [kWh/m ²]	Best fit	$G_A(\omega_{TA})$ [kWh/m ²]	ΔTIG_A [%]	ΔG_A [%]
1	2.26	2453	3078	$\omega_{TA}^\omega \begin{cases} a_0 = 8.1^\circ \\ a_{BT} = 8.1^\circ \end{cases}$	3016	9.9	2.0
2.1	2.55	2180	2715	$\omega_{TA}^\omega \begin{cases} a_0 = 4.0^\circ \\ a_{BT} = 4.0^\circ \end{cases}$	2693	4.2	0.8
2.2	2.55	2206	2749	$\omega_{TA}^\omega \begin{cases} a_0 = 4.0^\circ \\ a_{BT} = 7.0^\circ \end{cases}$	2719	5.7	1.1
3	2.26	2058	2514	$\omega_{TA}^L \begin{cases} b_0 = 0.3 \\ b_{BT} = 0.3 \end{cases}$	2481	7.2	1.3
4.1	3.00	2245	2983	$\omega_{TA}^L \begin{cases} b_0 = 0.55 \\ b_{BT} = 0.55 \end{cases}$	2923	8.2	2.0
4.2	3.00	2245	2983	$\omega_{TA}^L \begin{cases} b_0 = 0.50 \\ b_{BT} = 0.50 \end{cases}$	2929	7.3	1.8
5	2.56	1935	2505	$\omega_{TA}^L \begin{cases} b_0 = 0.38 \\ b_{BT} = 0.38 \end{cases}$	2457	8.3	1.9
6.1	2.71	1853	2397	$\omega_{TA}^\beta \begin{cases} c_0 = 0.0^\circ \\ c_{BT} = -3.0^\circ \end{cases}$	2368	5.4	1.2
6.2	2.71	1853	2401	$\omega_{TA}^\beta \begin{cases} c_0 = 0.0^\circ \\ c_{BT} = -3.0^\circ \end{cases}$	2372	5.4	1.2
7	2.74	1927	2431	$\omega_{TA}^L \begin{cases} b_0 = 0.52 \\ b_{BT} = 0.52 \end{cases}$	2382	9.9	2.0

enable this additional hidden loss due to backtracking to be anticipated during the design phase.

However, it is worth noting that many current utility-scale PV plants are being installed on sloping terrain [28]. We are investigating issues related to backtracking in some of these installations, which instead rely on standard horizontal ones (2D) [29]. The same simplification was often used in initial energy yield studies. We have analysed PV plants that use this type of adjustment, which is effective in areas with fairly uniform slopes. The loss in these plants can also be analysed using the above mechanisms, since SISIFO allows trackers to be simulated on uniform slopes. However, significant shading can result during backtracking periods when the terrain is much more irregular, as can be observed in Fig. 13. This can potentially affect energy capture. A key challenge for these plants is to deploy slope-aware (3D) tracking

algorithms to avoid shading. Also, market evolution is expected to mitigate this issue in the near future, as some commercial products already implement accurate slope-aware tracking algorithms (e.g., ORUGA software developed by Sener [30]). Nevertheless, discrepancies may still persist between initial estimates, based on pre-construction topography, and actual performance due to modifications during civil works or terrain irregularities.

Detailed reporting on PV plants deployed on sloping terrain is therefore reserved for future work.

Finally, it should be noted that these approaches for sloping terrain, although providing improved adaptation to terrain, typically require detailed topographic modelling and independent tracker control strategies. These requirements may not always be implemented in practice, especially in PV plants on mostly horizontal terrain where topography

Fig. 12. Zoom of the morning BT period for nine real PV plants analysed during the spring equinox, showing the comparison between ω_{TA} and ω_{IDC} with the experimentally measured ω_E . (a) (Egypt) and (b–c) (Brazil) show a better fit with the empirical angles using ω_{TA}^ω ; (d) (Chile), (e) (Mexico), (f) (Spain), and (i) (Chile) using ω_{TA}^L ; and (g–h) (Spain) using ω_{TA}^β .

is relatively uniform and additional analysis may be economically unfeasible. Moreover, most existing PV plants do not have controller configurations that allow independent tracking angles, and therefore all trackers are kept at the same angle. In these cases, deliberately applying an overridden backtracking allows the uniform-angle requirement to be maintained while ensuring that areas most affected by slightly undulating terrain continue to avoid shading effects, as the resulting tracking angles are slightly more tilted. In such situations, the modelling approaches proposed in this work provide a practical way to anticipate production losses during the design phase for PV plants using conventional backtracking strategies and to explain additional

suboptimal backtracking losses due to slight terrain unevenness in existing PV plants that do not modify their tracking strategies.

5. Conclusions

The tracking irradiation gain observed in many utility-scale PV plants is often lower than expected from the simulation of their energy yield performed at the project design phase for addressing bankability. The analysis of rotation angle data recorded from trackers of different manufacturers and operating configurations across seven real PV plants, located in five different geographical regions and with approximately 1 GW of nominal capacity, revealed that the problem arises

Fig. 13. Pictures taken at a real utility-scale PV plant installed on sloping terrain during backtracking periods. The red arrows indicate that shading can affect up to half of the PV arrays ((a) and (b)), even more in some cases (c), and can also fully shade individual PV modules (d).

from the fact that the simulation typically assumes perfectly flat terrain, while real terrain has some degree of unevenness. This results in small variations in axis height among different trackers, which can cause mutual shading between certain rows. To prevent such shading, which would not only be visually noticeable but also reduce power output and potentially create hot spots, the rotation angles are overridden by slightly reducing their tilt. However, this implies a lower solar irradiance capture.

Looking to disclose what unevenness correction is overridden, we proceeded as a case of reverse-engineering. First, we postulated three different types of correction algorithms based, respectively, on directly overriding the rotation angle, on analytically overriding the distance between rows, and on overriding the target angle to account for a ground slope. Then, we analysed which one best fits the in-field observed angles. Finally, we implemented these algorithms in SISIFO, a PV simulation software (freely accessible at <https://sisifo.info>) developed by the IES-UPM, and we performed TIG simulations on the TMY of the plant sites. The resulting ΔTIG_A and ΔG_A values range, respectively, from 4%–10% and from 0.8%–2%. Large enough to significantly affect the profitability of PV plants. In PV plants simulated under the assumption of perfectly flat terrain, whether already installed or not, these percentage differences represent previously unaddressed suboptimal backtracking losses. The most frequent correction is overriding a distance between tracker rows lower than the real one when computing the tracking angles. That is, tracker controllers override the inter-row spacing input to obtain more tilted tracking angles that reduce shading effects. This is likely because it is particularly easy to implement in standard tracker controllers, because it does not require any software modification but only to vary input data without the need for specific algorithms to account for uneven terrain. However, it has not been

possible to establish a single method that consistently minimizes the differences between model predictions and measured data across all the analysed PV plants. Therefore, in cases where real tracker operational data are not available and the proposed modelling approaches are used for prediction or estimation purposes, the results obtained from the three models presented in this work can provide a reasonable range within which the actual tracking behaviour is likely to lie. Nevertheless, we propose to include the suboptimal backtracking losses in the simulation phase of the PV plant and to discuss the choice of the available overridden backtracking models with the installer, selecting one or another based on the specific terrain characteristics, while noting that different models generally lead to similar or comparable results.

Moreover, it should be noted that the suboptimal backtracking losses derived from this study are based on operational data from the analysed PV plants. When applied to a new PV plant, although they improve the match between real and simulated results, the actual losses will depend on the adjustments applied, the real terrain unevenness of the PV plant, and the user's experience in handling these algorithms. Furthermore, this approach is primarily applicable to solar plants in which all trackers operate at a common rotation angle, rather than to those employing independent control strategies.

Beyond the standard correction for terrain unevenness, additional energy losses are observed in practice, caused, for example, by shading from adjacent trackers and by electrical losses in shared MPPT channels when some trackers are immobilized due to control or communication failures. These additional tracking-related losses contributed around 2%–4% further reduction in energy yield, depending on the PV plant layout and operational quality. Combined with terrain-induced effects, the actual tracking behaviour can account for a substantial portion of the total observed deviations from simulated performance, which may

exceed 6% annually. These effects fall outside the scope of the proposed modelling approaches, which focus exclusively on the geometric impact of terrain unevenness on backtracking behaviour.

Importantly, these losses are particularly valuable from an economic standpoint, as they occur during periods without curtailment and when energy prices are typically higher. This makes even seemingly small deviations of 1%–3% in captured irradiation significant in terms of revenue. Moreover, such losses usually remain unnoticed by operators and plant owners, since the standard KPIs (PR and availability) inherently include these discrepancies. Because of this, tracker angles can be easily adjusted to eliminate visible shading while the corresponding reduction in total energy output often goes unnoticed.

It is worth noting that many utility-scale PV plants are currently being installed on sloping terrain. We are now investigating backtracking-related issues in some of these installations since the in-field analysis presented in this paper is restricted to PV plants installed on flat terrain. Many of these plants also use non-optimal angles for uniform sloping terrain. Therefore, the expected losses can be anticipated in the manner described in this paper, since these algorithms can also be used for uniform sloping terrain, as can the SISIFO algorithm. However, the applicability of the work described for sloping terrain is still under investigation, as applying these tracking angular overrides in such cases could result in significant shading or energy losses. Detailed reporting on PV plants deployed on sloping terrain is therefore reserved for future work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Juan Santamaría-Sancho: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Javier R. Ledesma:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Resources, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Data curation. **Javier Martín-Rueda:** Writing – review & editing, Validation, Software, Data curation. **Eduardo Lorenzo:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Supervision, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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